

Yuklangan hadli Hirota tipidagi tenglamani cheksiz zonali davriy funksiyalar sinfida integrallash

Integration of a loaded terminal Hirota-type equation in the class of periodic functions with infinite gap

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17624403>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda davriy cheksiz zonali funksiyalar sinfidagi yuklangan hadli Hirota tipidagi tenglamani integrallash uchun teskari spektral masalalar usuli qo'llaniladi. Olti marta uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi davriy cheksiz zonali funksiyalar sinfidagi cheksizta Dubrovin differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Koshi masalasining yechimga ega ekanligi isbotlangan. Koshi masalasining yechimi yetarlicha silliq boshlang'ich shartlarda har doim mavjud ekanligi isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nochiziqli Hirota tenglamasi, Dirak operatori, spektral berilganlar, Dubrovin differensial tenglamalar sistemasi, izlar formulasi.

Abstract. In this work, the method of inverse spectral problems is used to integrate a loaded Hirota-type equation in the class of periodic infinite-zone functions. It is proved that the Cauchy problem has a solution for a system of infinite Dubrovin differential equations in the class of periodic infinite-zone functions that are six times continuously differentiable. It is proved that the solution of the Cauchy problem always exists under sufficiently smooth initial conditions.

Keywords: The nonlinear Hirota equation, Dirac operator, spectral data, Dubrovin system of differential equations, trace formulas.

Ushbu

$$\begin{cases} p_t = a(t) [p_{xxx} - 6p_x(p^2 + q^2)] + b(t) [-q_{xx} + 2q(p^2 + q^2)] + c(t)q(x_0, t)p_x, \\ q_t = a(t) [q_{xxx} - 6q_x(p^2 + q^2)] + b(t) [p_{xx} - 2p(p^2 + q^2)] + c(t)q(x_0, t)q_x, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

yuklangan hadli Hirota tipidagi tenglamaning

$$\begin{cases} p(x, t)|_{t=0} = p_0(x), \quad q(x, t)|_{t=0} = q_0(x), \quad x \in R, \\ p_0(x + \pi) = p_0(x) \in C^6(R), \quad q_0(x + \pi) = q_0(x) \in C^6(R), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni hamda quyidagi

$$\begin{cases} p(x + \pi, t) = p(x, t), \quad q(x + \pi, t) = q(x, t), \quad x \in R, \quad t > 0, \\ p(x, t), q(x, t) \in C_x^3(t > 0) \cap C_t^1(t > 0) \cap C(t \geq 0). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

silliqlik sinfiga tegishli yechimini cheksiz zonali davriy funksiyalar sinfida topish masalasini qaraymiz. Bu yerda $a(t), b(t), c(t) \in C([0, \infty))$, $c(t) \neq 0$ berilgan uzluksiz chegaralangan funksiyalar, $x_0 \in R$.

(1)-(3) Koshi masalasining yechimini quyidagi

$$L(\tau, t)y \equiv By' + \Omega(x + \tau, t)y = \lambda y, \quad x, \tau \in R, t > 0, \quad (4)$$

Dirak operatori uchun teskari spektral masalalar usulidan foydalanib topish algoritmimni bayon qilamiz. Bu yerda

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Omega(x + \tau, t) = \begin{pmatrix} p(x + \tau, t) & q(x + \tau, t) \\ q(x + \tau, t) & -p(x + \tau, t) \end{pmatrix}, \quad y(x) = \begin{pmatrix} y_1(x) \\ y_2(x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

(4) Dirak differensial tenglamalar sistemasining $c(0, \lambda, \tau, t) = (1, 0)^T$ va $s(0, \lambda, \tau, t) = (0, 1)^T$ boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimlarini mos ravishda

$$c(x, \lambda, \tau, t) = (c_1(x, \lambda, \tau, t), c_2(x, \lambda, \tau, t))^T \quad \text{va}$$

$s(x, \lambda, \tau, t) = (s_1(x, \lambda, \tau, t), s_2(x, \lambda, \tau, t))^T$ kabi belgilaymiz.

$\Delta(\lambda, \tau, t) = c_1(\pi, \lambda, \tau, t) + s_2(\pi, \lambda, \tau, t)$ funksiyaga $L(\tau, t)$ operatorining Lyapunov funksiyasi deyiladi.

Bunda $(\lambda_{2n} - \lambda_{2n-1})$, $n \in Z$ intervallarga $L(\tau, t)$ operatorning lakunalari deb ataladi, λ_n , $n \in Z$ sonlar esa (4) Dirak differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun qo'yilgan davriy ($y(0) = y(\pi)$) va yarimdavriy ($y(0) = -y(\pi)$) chegaraviy masalalarning xos qiymatlari bo'ladi. (4) Dirak differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Dirixle ($y_1(0) = 0$, $y_1(\pi) = 0$) chegaraviy masalasining xos qiymatlarini $\xi_n(\tau, t)$, $n \in Z$ lar orqali belgilaymiz. Ma'lumki bu xos qiymatlar $s_1(\pi, \lambda, \tau, t) = 0$ tenglamaning ildizlari bo'lib, $\xi_n(\tau, t) \in [\lambda_{2n}, \lambda_{2n-1}]$, $n \in Z$ munosabat o'rinli bo'ladi.

1-ta'rif. Ushbu $\{\xi_n(\tau, t), \sigma_n(\tau, t) = \text{sgn}\{s_2(\pi, \xi_n) - c_1(\pi, \xi_n)\} = \pm 1, n \in Z\}$ to'plamga $L(\tau, t)$ Dirak operatorining spektral parametrlari deyiladi

2-ta'rif. Ushbu $\{\lambda_n(\tau, t), \xi_n(\tau, t), \sigma_n(\tau, t) = \pm 1, n \in Z\}$ to'plamga esa $L(\tau, t)$ Dirak operatorning spektral berilganlari deyiladi.

Quyidagi $L(\tau, 0)$ Dirak operatorini qaraylik:

$$L(\tau, 0)y \equiv By' + \Omega_0(x + \tau)y = \lambda y, \quad x, \tau \in R, t > 0,$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Omega_0(x + \tau) = \begin{pmatrix} p_0(x + \tau) & q_0(x + \tau) \\ q_0(x + \tau) & -p_0(x + \tau) \end{pmatrix}, \quad y(x) = \begin{pmatrix} y_1(x) \\ y_2(x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

To'g'ri spektral masalani yechib $L(\tau, 0)$ operatorning spektral berilganlarini $\{\lambda_n, \xi_n^0 = \xi_n^0(\tau), \sigma_n^0 = \sigma_n^0(\tau) = \pm 1, n \in Z\}$ topib olamiz. Bunda $L(\tau, 0)$ operatorning spektral parametrlari uchun $\xi_n^0(\tau + \pi) = \xi_n^0(\tau)$, $\sigma_n^0(\tau + \pi) = \sigma_n^0(\tau)$, $n \in Z$ davriylik shartlari o'rinli bo'ladi.

1-teorema. Agar $p(x, t)$, $q(x, t)$ funksiyalar (1)-(3) Koshi masalasining yechimi bo'lsa, u holda $L(\tau, t)$ operatorning spektri chetki nuqtalari $\lambda_n(\tau, t)$, $n \in Z$ lar τ va t parametrlarga bog'liq bo'lmaydi, ya'ni $\lambda_n(\tau, t) = \lambda_n$, $n \in Z$, $\tau \in R$, $t > 0$, uning spektral parametrlari $\xi_n(\tau, t)$, $\sigma_n(\tau, t) = \pm 1$, $n \in Z$ esa quyidagi birinchi va ikkinchi Dubrovin differensial tenglamalar sistemasi analoglarini qanoatlantiradi:

$$\frac{\partial \xi_n(\tau, t)}{\partial \tau} = 2(-1)^{n-1} \sigma_n(\tau, t) h_n(\xi(\tau, t)) \{p(\tau, t) + \xi_n(\tau, t)\}, \quad n \in Z, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \xi_n(\tau, t)}{\partial t} = 2(-1)^n \sigma_n(\tau, t) h_n(\xi(\tau, t)) g_n(\xi_n(\tau, t)), \quad n \in Z. \quad (6)$$

Bundan tashqari quyidagi boshlang'ich shartlar o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$\xi_n(\tau, t)|_{t=0} = \xi_n^0(\tau), \quad \sigma_n(\tau, t)|_{t=0} = \sigma_n^0(\tau), \quad n \in Z. \quad (7)$$

$h_n(\xi(\tau, t))$ va $g_n(\xi(\tau, t))$ funksiyalar ketma-ketliklari quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$h_n(\xi) = \sqrt{(\xi_n - \lambda_{2n-1})(\lambda_{2n} - \xi_n)} \cdot f_n(\xi), \quad f_n(\xi) = \sqrt{\prod_{\substack{k=-\infty \\ k \neq n}}^{+\infty} \frac{(\lambda_{2k-1} - \xi_n)(\lambda_{2k} - \xi_n)}{(\xi_k - \xi_n)^2}},$$

$$g_n(\xi) = a(t) \left[4\xi_n^3 + 4p\xi_n^2 + 2\xi_n(p^2 + q^2 + q_\tau) + 2(pq_\tau - p_\tau q) + 2p(p^2 + q^2) - p_{\tau\tau} \right] + b(t) \left[(\xi_n + p)^2 + q^2 + q_\tau + \xi_n^2 \right] - c(t)q(x_0, t) [\xi_n + p], \quad n \in Z.$$

Bu yerda $p = p(\tau, t)$, $q = q(\tau, t)$, $\xi_n = \xi_n(\tau, t)$, $n \in Z$.

Quyidagi

$$p(\tau, t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda_{2k-1} + \lambda_{2k}}{2} - \xi_k(\tau, t) \right), \quad (8)$$

$$q(\tau, t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} (-1)^{k-1} \sigma_k(\tau, t) h_k(\xi(\tau, t)), \quad (9)$$

izlar formulalari va ushbu

$$\xi_n(\tau, t) = \lambda_{2n-1} + (\lambda_{2n} - \lambda_{2n-1}) \sin^2 x_n(\tau, t), \quad n \in Z$$

almashtirishdan foydalanib (6)-(7) Koshi masalasini quyidagi ko'rinishga keltirish mumkin:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx(\tau, t)}{dt} = H(x(\tau, t)), \\ x(\tau, t)|_{t=0} = x^0(\tau), \quad x^0(\tau) \in K. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Bu yerda

$$K = \left\{ x(\tau, t) = (\dots, x_{-1}(\tau, t), x_0(\tau, t), x_1(\tau, t), \dots) : \|x(\tau, t)\| = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} (1 + |n|^2) \gamma_n |x_n(\tau, t)| < \infty \right\},$$

$$H(x(\tau, t)) = (\dots, H_{-1}(x(\tau, t)), H_0(x(\tau, t)), H_1(x(\tau, t)), \dots),$$

$$H_n(x(\tau, t)) = (-1)^n \sigma_n^0(\tau) f_n(\dots, \lambda_{-1} + (\lambda_0 - \lambda_{-1}) \sin^2 x_0(\tau, t), \dots) \times$$

$$\times g_n(\dots, \lambda_{-1} + (\lambda_0 - \lambda_{-1}) \sin^2 x_0(\tau, t), \dots), \quad \sigma_n^0(\tau) = \sigma_n(\tau, t) \operatorname{sgn} \{ \sin x_n(\tau, t) \cos x_n(\tau, t) \},$$

$$x^0(\tau) = (\dots, x_{-1}^0(\tau), x_0^0(\tau), x_1^0(\tau), \dots), \quad x_n^0(\tau) = \arcsin \sqrt{\frac{\xi_n^0(\tau) - \lambda_{2n-1}}{\lambda_{2n} - \lambda_{2n-1}}}, \quad n \in Z.$$

(10) Koshi masalasi K Banax fazosida yagona yechimga ega bo'lishi uchun $H(x(\tau, t))$ funksiya K Banax fazosida Lipshist shartini qanoatlantirishi yetarli, ya'ni

$$\forall x(\tau, t), y(\tau, t) \in K, \exists N > 0, \|H(x(\tau, t)) - H(y(\tau, t))\| \leq N \|x(\tau, t) - y(\tau, t)\|.$$

Ma'lumki, $p_0(x + \pi) = p_0(x) \in C^6(R)$, $q_0(x + \pi) = q_0(x) \in C^6(R)$ shartlar o'rinli bo'lganda (4) tenglamaga qo'yilgan davriy va yarimdavriy chegaraviy masalalarning xos qiymatlari uchun [5]

$$\lambda_{2k}, \lambda_{2k-1} = k + \sum_{j=1}^7 c_j k^{-j} \pm 2^{-6} |k|^{-6} \cdot |q_{2k}^6| + |k|^{-6} \cdot \varepsilon_k^\pm,$$

$$\gamma_k \equiv \lambda_{2k} - \lambda_{2k-1} = \frac{|q_{2k}^6|}{2^5 |k|^6} + \frac{\delta_k}{k^7}, \quad \delta_k = \varepsilon_k^+ - \varepsilon_k^-, |q_{2k}^6|, \delta_k \in l_2$$

asimptotik formulalar o'rinli bo'ladi. Demak $\xi_n(\tau, t) \in [\lambda_{2n-1}, \lambda_{2n}]$, $n \in Z$ lar uchun quyidagi munosabat o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$\inf_{k \neq n} |\xi_n(\tau, t) - \xi_k(\tau, t)| \geq a > 0.$$

1-lemma. Quyidagi tengsizliklar o'rinli: [1]-[4]

$$1) C_1 \leq |f_n(x)| \leq C_2, \quad \left| \frac{\partial f_n(x)}{\partial x_m} \right| \leq C_3 \gamma_m,$$

$$2) |g_n(x)| \leq C_4 (|n|^3 + 1), \quad \left| \frac{\partial g_n(x)}{\partial x_m} \right| \leq C_5 \gamma_m (|m|^2 + |n|^2 + |m||n| + 1).$$

Bu yerda, $x = (\dots, x_{-1}, x_0, x_1, \dots)$, $C_j = \text{const}$, $j = \overline{1, 5}$.

2-lemma. Agar $p_0(x + \pi) = p_0(x) \in C^6(R)$, $q_0(x + \pi) = q_0(x) \in C^6(R)$ bo'lsa, u holda $H(x(\tau, t))$ vektor-funksiya K Banax fazosida Lipsht shartini qanoatlantradi, ya'ni $\exists N = \text{const} > 0$ soni topilib $\forall x(\tau, t), y(\tau, t) \in K$ elementlar uchun

$$\|H(x(\tau, t)) - H(y(\tau, t))\| \leq N \|x(\tau, t) - y(\tau, t)\|,$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi. Bu yerda $N = C_6 \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} \gamma_k (1 + |k|^2) (|k|^3 + 1)$.

1-natija. 1-teorema va 2-lemma (1)-(3) Koshi masalasini yechish algoritmini hosil qiladi.

1) Buning uchun avvalo $L(\tau, 0)$ Dirak operatori spektral berilganlari $\{\lambda_n, \xi_n(\tau), \sigma_n^0(\tau) = \pm 1, n \in Z\}$ aniqlaymiz;

2) $L(\tau, t)$ operatorning spektral berilganlari $\{\lambda_n, \xi_n(\tau, t), \sigma_n(\tau, t) = \pm 1, n \in Z\}$ ko'rinishda belgilab olamiz. (6)-(7) Koshi masalasini $\tau = x_0$ nuqtada yechib $\xi_n(x_0, t), \sigma_n(x_0, t) = \pm 1, n \in Z$ larni topamiz;

3) Topilganlarni (8), (9) izlar formulalariga qo'yib $q(x_0, t)$ funksiyani aniqlab olamiz;

4) Topilgan $q(x_0, t)$ funksiyani (6) Dubrovin differensial tenglamalar sistemasiga qo'yib $\forall \tau \in R$ larda (6)-(7) Koshi masalasini yechib $L(\tau, t)$ Dirak operatorining spektral parametrlari $\xi_n(\tau, t), \sigma_n(\tau, t) = \pm 1, n \in Z$ larni aniqlaymiz. (8), (9) izlar formulalaridan foydalanib (6)-(7) Koshi masalasining $p(\tau, t), q(\tau, t)$ yechimlarini topamiz.

2-teorema. Agar $p_0(x)$ va $q_0(x)$ funksiyalar quyidagi

$$p_0(x + \pi) = p_0(x) \in C^6(R), \quad q_0(x + \pi) = q_0(x) \in C^6(R)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantirsa, u holda (1)-(3) Koshi masalasining $p(x,t), q(x,t) \in C_x^3(t > 0) \cap C_t^1(t > 0) \cap C(t \geq 0)$ sinfiga tegishli yagona global yechimi mavjud va u (8), (9) izlar formulalari yordamida topiladi.

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